

2. Effect of sesbania straw on water-soluble nutrients in a flooded Crowley silt loam soil in the laboratory. Louisiana State University, 1987.

dry soil, with and without sesbania straw, were transferred into 50-ml centrifuge tubes (25 × 100 ml) fitted with rubber septa. The soil samples were submerged with 25 ml of deionized distilled water. The tubes were weighed and incubated at 30°C. Moisture lost during incubation was replaced by weighing the tubes occasionally and adding water as needed.

At specified intervals, the tubes were shaken for 30 min, centrifuged at 7,000 rev/min for 20 min, and the solutions filtered through 0.45-µm filter paper. The samples were acidified to pH 2 with 12 N HCl and analyzed for different elements on an Inductive Coupled Argon Plasma emission spectrophotometer.

Decreases in soil Eh after flooding were more pronounced with the addition of sesbania straw (Fig. 1). At 60 d after flooding (DF), soil Eh decreased to -125 without sesbania and to -245 mV with sesbania. The Eh of the soil receiving sesbania stabilized at

30 DF, the Eh in unamended samples stabilized at 40 DF.

Increased soil reduction caused by incorporation of sesbania straw was also reflected by increases in soil pH. At 60 DF, soil pH increased from 6.8 to 7.2 without sesbania and to 7.4 with sesbania.

Incorporation of sesbania straw had a

variable effect on the release of water-soluble nutrients in the flooded soil (Fig. 2). Sesbania application caused marked increases of water-soluble Ca, Mg, P, Fe, and Mn. Those increases peaked 4 to 8 DF, then decreased. Sesbania straw had a slightly depressing effect on water-soluble Cu, Zn, and Al, but had no effect on water-soluble Si. □

Amelioration of highly alkali soil by karnal grass and para grass before rice - wheat cropping sequence

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To reclaim alkali soils (pH greater than 10), 12-15 t gypsum/ha followed by rice - wheat for 3-4 yr has been recommended. But gypsum is costly for small and marginal farmers.

We studied growing karnal grass [*Diplachne fusca* (Linn.) P. Beauv] and

para grass [*Brachiaria mutica* (Forsk.) Stapf.] as alternatives to gypsum.

The field was highly alkaline: pH 10.6 and exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP) 94. Soil texture was sandy loam with 15% clay, 27% silt, and 58% sand. The experiment was conducted 1979-80 to 1983-84 in a split-plot design with four replications. The eight treatments are in the table.

Jaya rice and HD2009 wheat were sown throughout. Gypsum was applied 19 Jun 1979. Karnal grass and para grass were planted 8 Jul 1979.

Recommended agronomic practices for growing rice and wheat in alkali soil were followed.

The results indicate that grasses grown for 2 yr sufficiently ameliorated the soil for a successful rice-wheat sequence. Rice yields in plots without amendment were possible the third year, and wheat yields the fourth year. Yields of rice and wheat in plots where 12.5 t gypsum/ha was applied and where karnal grass was grown for 2 yr did not differ significantly.

Changes of soil pH as a result of the treatments are shown in the figure. The pH reduction was greatest in plots

Rice - wheat yields in alkali soil treated with gypsum or grass crops. Haryana, India, 1979-84.

Treatment ^a	Yield (t/ha)									
	1979-80		1980-81		1981-82		1982-83		1983-84	
	Rice	Wheat	Rice	Wheat	Rice	Wheat	Rice	Wheat	Rice	Wheat
No amendment	0	0	1.0	0	4.6	0.6	5.7	2.7	5.1	3.8
Gypsum	3.7	2.6	4.5	1.3	5.8	3.4	6.5	3.6	4.8	4.6
P 1 yr	—	—	3.8	0.1	5.8	1.6	6.8	3.3	5.4	4.7
P 2 yr	—	—	—	—	5.3	2.6	5.9	3.4	5.1	4.9
P 3 yr	—	—	—	—	—	—	5.6	3.0	5.9	4.3
K 1 yr	—	—	4.1	0.3	5.4	2.1	6.6	3.6	5.4	4.6
K 2 yr	—	—	—	—	6.1	3.4	5.8	3.8	5.2	5.2
K 3 yr	—	—	—	—	—	—	5.8	3.2	5.5	4.1
CD (0.05)	—	—	—	—	—	—	ns	0.5	0.5	0.6

^aP = para grass, K = karnal grass.

where gypsum was applied. For the grasses, pH reduction was greater in

plots where karnal grass was grown for 2 yr. □

Effect of pyrite and fertilizer on rice protein quality

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Protein concentration in grain increases with high fertility. Because the poor biological value of rice protein is

attributed to the deficiency of essential amino acids, such as lysine and tryptophan, we studied the effect of different levels of pyrite and fertilizer on protein quality of rice.

The soil was slightly saline-alkali with moderate pH and exchangeable sodium percentage. Pyrite was applied 10 d before transplanting Saket 4 to ensure complete oxidation in the experimental field. N as urea, single superphosphate, and muriate of potash were applied.

Half the N and all the P and potash were applied at transplanting. The remaining N was applied 30 d after transplanting.

Grain samples were harvested with a sickle and dried in an oven at 60 °C. The samples were hand pounded to brown rice, ground to powder, and passed through a 60-mesh sieve for chemical analysis. N content in the defatted samples was determined by microKjeldahl method; that value was